

Integrated pest management—weeds

Effect of nitrogen uptake by weeds on rice yield

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Nitrogen use efficiency in rice is low when weeds compete; that reduces rice yield. Farmers need an economic threshold, when weed control practices would be profitable. We experimented with different weed populations in rice in Joydebpur in 1988 and 1990.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 1 m². Thirty-day-old BR23 seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Weeds were allowed to grow with rice from the 2- to 3-leaf stage at eight weed densities (unwanted weeds were removed). Recommended fertilizer for transplanted aman (wet season second crop) rice was applied.

At maturity, weeds were removed, cleaned, and identified. Weed dry weights and N uptake were determined. Rice grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Fimbristylis miliacea was the dominant weed species, followed by *Sphenoclea zeylanica*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Scirpus mucronatus*, and *Heteranthera limosa*.

Best fit regression models based on average data were used to determine N uptake and yield loss of rice at different weed densities.

As weed density increased, the weeds took up more N and rice less (Fig. 1). This was reflected in grain yield (Fig. 2). Yield losses were 13% with 20 weeds/m² and 17% with 40 weeds/m². □

1. Effect of weed density on N uptake (kg/ha) by weeds and rice.

2. Effect of weed density on rice grain yield.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Crushing snail eggs with a “snail egg clapper”

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The golden apple snail *Pomacea lineata* Spix. is a major rice pest in the Philippines. It can cause total destruction of germinating rice seedlings and more than

20% damage in young seedlings. It can be controlled with organotin molluscicides, but these chemicals are toxic to human beings, livestock, and aquatic life.